

The Innovation of Sharing Mode of Clothing Industries in the Internet Age

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ABSTRACT

With the development of the Internet and the emergence of the sharing economy, China's clothing industries have entered a more challenging and more competitive environment. Now many traditional clothing enterprises do not integrate their resources well. In this article, through the interpretation of the development format and the theoretical basis of the sharing economy of China's clothing enterprises, the way of using offline design, platform sharing and offline production will be traditional. This paper analyzes the innovative mode of clothing production combining with the Internet and the current popular sharing economy.

KEYWORDS: *the innovation; clothing industries; the Internet age; sharing code*

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INTRODUCTION

with the advent of the information age, the new economic mode based on the "Internet +" - the shared economy, has been constantly attacking traditional economic patterns and consumption concepts, and has become a new growth area. Sharing bicycles, cars, and many other sharing concepts are also being understood and accepted by more and more people. The concept of sharing permeates all aspects of our lives from online and offline. The complexity of the clothing industry has led to higher requirements for the competitiveness of clothing enterprises, such as the shortening of product popularity cycle. Based on the development situation of China's clothing industry and the theoretical basis of sharing economy, this paper analyzes the sharing mode and current situation of clothing enterprises, as well as the opportunities and challenges they are facing, and explores the sustainable development path of characteristic sharing mode.

1. The current situation and characteristics of traditional clothing enterprises

1.1. Traditional clothing enterprises can not meet the more and more personalized needs of consumers

The homogenization of traditional garment enterprises is serious, and the market positioning is unclear. Once a garment is welcomed by consumers in the market, a large number of garment manufacturers will follow the trend and organize proofing and production immediately after getting the garment information. In a short time, a large number of popular items of the same type appear in the streets and lanes. Today's consumers are very personalized and don't

like to run into other people's shirts. They hope to show their style and personality by their clothing. Obviously, the function of clothing has changed from covering body and keeping warm to the symbol of spirit and identity.

1.2 The long industrial chain of traditional clothing enterprises leads to the failure of fast response of clothing supply chain

The traditional clothing industry chain "factory-brand-company-agent-Retailer-consumer" has many shortcomings, such as many intermediate links, high procurement cost, large use of personnel, opaque price, untimely supply, professional mismatch, leading to severe forms. The fast fashion management strategy of the clothing industry shortens the popular life cycle, and the demand is increasing day by day. The fast response clothing supply chain is needed to match with it, so as to improve the communication efficiency among enterprises, promote effective market prediction, shorten the operation cycle of the supply chain, and realize the maximization of the self and overall interests of the clothing supply chain enterprises.

1.3 The cost of traditional clothing enterprises is high because of the lack of perfect integration of resources in the whole industry chain.

Most of the garment enterprises today have a single development mode, most of which have no innovation mode, and cannot meet the needs of market changes and integrate well. Although the current garment enterprises, driven by the development of "Internet +", have begun to use various

kinds of e-commerce channels to build their own official mall, enter the platform or enter micro shops. But most of them are independent. The links such as production or sales are connected with the Internet, which does not realize the resource integration of the entire industrial chain, nor does it make good use of the Internet. Garment manufacturing is mainly based on large orders and large customers. Products from the factory pass through multi-level distributors and retail stores, and there will be corresponding costs between each link.

2. Sharing mode of clothing enterprises in the Internet Age

2.1. Put forward the sharing mode of clothing enterprises

We put forward such a mode, which is different from the mass production mode of traditional clothing enterprises. Each enterprise can share the designers and production factories of other companies to break the design barriers and production barriers. And through the combination of MTM system construction and clothing customization, we can share the existing clothing pattern and integrate the existing resources of the clothing industry to make the most of it.

2.2. Using steps of sharing mode in garment enterprises

Diagram1. How customers use It

Diagram2.how enterprises use it

Diagram3.how designers use it

2.3. Advantages of sharing mode of clothing enterprises in the Internet Era

2.3.1. It can meet people's personalized needs well.

Online design platform can help consumers customize unique clothes. For example, the air force series shoes are customized on Nike's official website, and consumers can choose their own color and pattern.

2.3.2. It can Shorten the production process.

For garment enterprises, through the steps of online sharing platform to release demand, match designers, determine cooperation, sign contracts, and confirm results by stages, they can complete the garment production once, greatly simplifying the long communication process of traditional

MTM (make to measure) system is a general term of technical devices for individual design, model and manufacturing.

First of all, we will establish a platform for fashion design exchange. Consumers, professional designers and people with fashion design dreams can communicate directly. Due to the sharing and openness of the platform, garment manufacturers can place orders through the platform, select the design drawings they like in the design library provided by the platform, buy them, and then send them to the garment factory for production and processing or through the production factory with cooperation with the platform. This sharing mode provides a large number of high-quality clothing design drawings for small and medium-sized clothing enterprises. Through design outsourcing and production outsourcing, small and medium-sized clothing enterprises reduce costs and operational risks, and improve product quality. Among them, our sharing platform will provide rights protection services for each design drawing, respect and guarantee the designer's achievements, and let the designer enjoy the opportunities brought by the platform more confidently.

garment industry, shortening the production cycle of orders, more in line with the current pursuit of fast fashion, and occupying the market for garment enterprises.

2.3.3. Reduce the cost of the enterprise accordingly.

Because there is a sharing platform for resource information sharing, coupled with the shortening of the industrial chain, many unnecessary costs are reduced.

3. The feasibility of clothing enterprises sharing mode in the Internet Era

3.1 Improved the economic level of consumers creates a potential market for clothing consumption

With the improvement of people's living standards and the improvement of per capita income, the expenditure of

Chinese residents for clothing consumption will maintain a stable growth. According to the data of the National Bureau of statistics, from January to April 2018, the per capita clothing expenditure level of urban residents increased from 1553.70 yuan in 2017 to 1627.20 yuan in January to April 2018, with an annual growth rate of 4.73%; the per capita clothing expenditure level of rural residents increased from 453.80 yuan in 2017 to 510.40 yuan in January to April 2018, with an annual growth rate of 12.47%.

3.2. The influence of Internet red economy on consumers

With its unique advantages, the online live broadcasting platform promotes the development of netred economy, which regards fans as the main consumer group. The fans they have are all fond of and infatuated with them. They will turn their trust and love for netred into buying the products she represents and sells. The loyalty of fans to their favorite online celebrities is much higher than that of ordinary consumers, and their repeat purchase rate and attention to stores and commodities will correspondingly become higher. This kind of net red economy has opened up a new mode of clothing sales for the new mode of clothing industry sharing.

3.3. The emergence and development of Internet +

With the development of "Internet +", there are multiple platforms on the Internet that can customize garments for customers according to the MTM system. For example, the current e-commerce platform has already customized patterns according to customers' preferences on clothing and shoes.

4. Problems in the sharing mode of garment enterprises

4.1. Low public awareness of the new model

Clothing sharing mode belongs to the new operation mode of clothing design, production and sales. No matter consumers, clothing brands and fashion designers have little knowledge of the new mode. As far as garment enterprises are concerned, because the mode of garment sharing is still in the exploratory stage, there are no particularly successful cases at present, most of them have not been exposed to this new mode, and some of them dare not apply this mode rashly. As far as consumers are concerned, they are accustomed to buying clothes on familiar platforms or other channels, and they know little about the new model, or even don't know that the new model exists.

4.2. Problems arising from outsourcing of order production

We adopt the order completion method of separation of production and design. Once the enterprise placing the order passes the designer's design, the designer will no longer be responsible for the quality supervision of production, and the rest of production issues will be followed up by the platform broker one by one. This has a great impact on the order production time and quality control. First, without its own production plant, all orders on the platform need to be produced by the clothing production plant with cooperative relationship, that is, production outsourcing. Second, the poor communication between the clothing brand and the production plant will also lead to the uncontrollable quality of the products. Third, the process of the production plant is not transparent, and the clothing brand can only inform all the progress of the order through the platform broker, the passive party.

5. Methods of resolution

5.1. Using Internet model to improve public awareness

First of all, microblog can be used for the new mode of pre transmission. On microblog, we can expand the popularity of the new model by buying hot search, inviting bloggers with a certain number of fans to promote, winning a lottery and other ways to attract the attention of young consumers to the new model. Next, we can use WeChat public address to publish articles on clothing produced in the new mode. For example, publish articles on the tips of clothing matching, insert soft advertisements of new patterns in these articles that introduce dressing skills, or place hyperlinks to wechat shopping malls at the bottom of each article. Finally, the new model can also be advertised in app. For example, in video playing app advertising, users must accept more than ten seconds of advertising before using this app to watch video. This kind of forced advertisement is hard to forget after several times of circulation.

5.2. Using stars as spokesmen to improve public awareness

Star endorsement is a way of advertising with its own sales volume. First, stars often have a certain fan base, and the "star effect" brought by star endorsement is powerful. Second, stars often bring their own enthusiasm. When stars participate in variety shows, interviews, movies and TV plays, they will constantly promote the new model. For example, in a variety show, the clothes he wears will repeatedly appear in front of the audience in an hour or two, and the audience will improve their familiarity with a certain dress. In this way, the new model can be used to promote its platform model by a certain garment.

5.3. Using encryption technology to solve management problems

The information of clothing enterprises, customers' body data and private information are all private information. First, the platform needs to establish a complete and secure information protection mechanism to protect these information for customers. Second, the platform needs to establish a strict supervision mechanism for staff to prevent internal staff from disclosing customer information for personal interests.

5.4 Use existing sales platform to solve sales problems

A. At present, the development of the new model is in the new stage of prosperity, with few consumers, incomplete market mechanism and lack of sales channels. In the early stage of the development of the new model, garment enterprises can rely on the existing large-scale shopping platforms such as Taobao, Alibaba, Amazon, etc. to expand the sales scope and channels while ensuring the quality; in the later stage, after maintaining customer loyalty, they should establish their own websites, see the combination of enterprise culture and product sales, to provide the added value of products and the cultural connotation of enterprises.

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